

Easy One-Step Amplification and Labeling Procedure for Copy Number Variation Detection

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BACKGROUND: The specific characteristics of copy number variations (CNVs) require specific methods of detection and characterization. We developed the Easy One-Step Amplification and Labeling procedure for CNV detection (EOSAL-CNV), a new method based on proportional amplification and labeling of amplicons in 1 PCR.

METHODS: We used tailed primers for specific amplification and a pair of labeling probes (only 1 labeled) for amplification and labeling of all amplicons in just 1 reaction. Products were loaded directly onto a capillary DNA sequencer for fragment sizing and quantification. Data obtained could be analyzed by Microsoft Excel spreadsheet or EOSAL-CNV analysis software. We developed the protocol using the *LDLR* (low density lipoprotein receptor) gene including 23 samples with 8 different CNVs. After optimizing the protocol, it was used for genes in the following multiplexes: *BRCA1* (BRCA1 DNA repair associated), *BRCA2* (BRCA2 DNA repair associated), *CHEK2* (checkpoint kinase 2), *MLH1* (mutL homolog 1) plus *MSH6* (mutS homolog 6), *MSH2* (mutS homolog 2) plus *EPCAM* (epithelial cell adhesion molecule) and chromosome 17 (especially the *TP53* [tumor protein 53] gene). We compared our procedure with multiplex ligation-dependent probe amplification (MLPA).

RESULTS: The simple procedure for CNV detection required 150 min, with <10 min of handwork. After analyzing >240 samples, EOSAL-CNV excluded the presence of CNVs in all controls, and in all cases, results

were identical using MLPA and EOSAL-CNV. Analysis of the 17p region in tumor samples showed 100% similarity between fluorescent in situ hybridization and EOSAL-CNV.

CONCLUSIONS: EOSAL-CNV allowed reliable, fast, easy detection and characterization of CNVs. It provides an alternative to targeted analysis methods such as MLPA.

Introduction

Copy number variations (CNVs) are DNA variations involving 50 bp or more that show a variable number of copies compared to a reference genome (1). In general, CNVs occur along the whole genome and include large rearrangements involving gain or loss of DNA sequences such as duplications, amplifications, and deletions. In the broadest sense, CNVs can include structural variations with these characteristics (2).

The human genome contains many CNVs, some of which are involved in complex diseases many others causing inherited diseases (3–5). Familial hypercholesterolemia (FH; Online Mendelian Inheritance in Man [OMIM] 143890), hereditary breast cancer (OMIM 114480), and Lynch syndrome (OMIM 120435) are examples of inherited diseases caused by heterozygous CNVs (6–8). In addition, many somatic CNVs are involved in the development, evolution, and treatment response of a variety of cancers (9).

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CNVs have been screened and studied using diverse techniques. Some have been used mainly for structural variations as cytogenetic techniques, such as karyotyping, fluorescent in situ hybridization (FISH), or comparative genomic hybridization. These techniques have limited application in CNV detection in single genes or small regions and are mainly for those altering a part of the region or gene of interest (10–12). Another group consists of molecular techniques for targeted screening, such as Southern blot, long PCR, quantitative PCR, paralogue ratio test, molecular copy-number counting, multiplex amplifiable probe hybridization, multiplex ligation-dependent probe amplification (MLPA), quantitative multiplex PCR of short fluorescent fragments (QMPSF), universal primer quantitative fluorescent multiplex PCR (UPQFM-PCR), or multiplex amplicon quantification (MAQ) (2). Each technique has its own advantages and drawbacks. Southern blot, for example, requires a considerable amount of DNA, manual steps, and turnaround time, and long PCR is unable to detect many CNVs and needs a specific design for most (although it is a good option for screening a particular CNV) (1). Real-time quantitative PCR needs many reactions for a single locus, and the results can be difficult to reproduce (13–16). QMPSF and UPQFM-PCR can analyze only a limited number of fragments (17, 18). Currently, MLPA is the most widely used method of this group, and the main technique used for the study of CNVs in genes related to hereditary diseases (10, 19). MLPA has been developed for many genes (17, 20, 21). The main drawback of MLPA is the need for different steps, requiring considerable manual processing and several days to get the results.

Large-scale techniques such as microchips and next-generation sequencing have been used recently for CNV detection (8, 22–27). Both techniques can detect CNVs but have their own drawbacks: they allow limited detection of small CNVs involving a part of 1 gene, they are expensive and time-consuming, and their capacity is disputed depending on the different approaches used (26–29). It should be noted that detection of CNV by MLPA or high-throughput techniques such as microchips or next-generation sequencing requires validation by another technique, especially for genetic diagnosis (2, 27).

Given the increasing importance of CNV determination for many diseases, we developed the Easy One-Step Amplification and Labeling procedure for CNV detection (EOSAL-CNV) to detect and characterize CNVs (Fig. 1). EOSAL-CNV is based on only 1 PCR, with specific primer and labeling probes (only 1 labeled probe) allowing proportional and reproducible amplification of each target region. In this study, we tested the

method in several human genes involving heterozygous CNVs that cause hereditary diseases.

Materials and Methods

PCR DESIGN

We designed specific PCR primers for amplifying DNA fragments in the promoter and exons of *LDLR* (low density lipoprotein receptor), *BRCA1* (BRCA1 DNA repair associated), *BRCA2* (BRCA2 DNA repair associated), *MLH1* (mutL homolog 1), *MSH2* (mutS homolog 2), and *MSH6* (mutS homolog 6) genes; *CHEK2* (checkpoint kinase 2) exons 1 and 9; *EPCAM* (epithelial cell adhesion molecule) exons 8 and 9; and chromosome 17 (Chr17), especially the 17p region and the *TP53* (tumor protein 53) gene. We included other genetic regions as internal controls in each reaction (see Supplemental Table 1 in the online Data Supplement). For primer design, we excluded regions with polymorphisms with minor allele frequency >0.1%. The amplicons were required to differ in length from each other by at least 3 bp in each reaction. Primers were designed with Primer3 software (30) including 1 tail in each primer. We included a probe for the tails, one labeled with 6-FAM (6-carboxyfluorescein) and the other without labeling.

The procedure and protocol were developed using the *LDLR* gene as a model. Next, we validated the procedure in the remaining genes in 2 steps: (a) testing differences in peak intensity using 12.5, 25, and 50 ng of total DNA in each reaction, and (b) analyzing control samples (without CNVs) and validating each of the previously indicated genes (Supplemental Table 2) in control and patient (with CNVs) samples, organized into the following multiplexes: *BRCA1*, *BRCA2-CHEK2*, *EPCAM-MSH2*, *MLH1-MSH6*, and chr17. PCR reactions were performed in Applied Biosystems 2720 and Veriti thermocyclers (Thermo Fisher). A size marker was included for fragment analysis (LIZ500; Thermo Fisher). Capillary electrophoresis was performed in an Applied Biosystems 3730 DNA Analyzer using a 36-cm capillary array and POP7 polymer under standard conditions for fragment analysis by G5 matrix.

DNA SAMPLES

This study was approved by the ethics committee of Clinic Hospital of Valencia (Valencia, Spain), and all patients and control participants provided written informed consent for this study or for sample donation to a biobank.

Samples from patients with FH and controls included in this study were provided by the Endocrinology Service (Clinic Hospital of Valencia); the other samples were provided by the IBSP-CV BioBank

Fig. 1. Schematic representation of the EOSAL-CNV process for amplification and labeling. Representation of reaction performed in 1 PCR including reagents for PCR and amplification primer pairs (each has a specific sequence for amplifying the target region and a tail) and labeling probes (probes for amplifying and labeling all amplicons using the tails). In initial steps, primers amplify specific regions, and once the tails are incorporated in a small number of amplicons, the reaction allows simultaneous amplification and labeling.

(PT13/0010/0064), part of the Spanish National Biobanks Network, the Valencian Biobanking Network, and the Basque Biobank. Samples and data were processed following standard operating procedures, and approvals of the ethics and scientific committees were

obtained. Information from the biobanks included the gene with a CNV or CNV description, as detected by MLPA. [Supplemental Table 2](#) shows the samples included in this study, previous data on the CNVs, and the CNVs found by MLPA and EOSAL-CNV. A total

of 241 samples were included: 23 samples with 8 different CNVs in the *LDLR* gene, 52 samples with 14 different CNVs in *BRCA1*, 8 samples with 4 CNVs in *BRCA2* and *CHEK2*, 10 samples with 4 CNVs in *MLH1* and *MSH6*, 20 samples with 10 CNVs in *MSH2* and *EPCAM*, and 8 samples with structural variations in chr17 affecting the *TP53* gene. In addition, we analyzed 20 control samples for each reaction.

We extracted genomic DNA from control participants (individuals without CNVs in the genes analyzed); patients with FH caused by CNVs in the *LDLR* gene; patients with hereditary breast cancer caused by different CNVs in *BRCA1*, *BRCA2* or *CHEK2*; patients with Lynch syndrome, caused by CNVs in *MLH1*, *MSH2*, or *EPCAM*; and patients with chronic lymphocytic leukemia for chr17 study (see Supplemental Table 2).

Samples were extracted by different procedures such as phenol-chloroform, chemogenic (Chemagen), and Maxwell (Promega). CNVs in patients with FH and controls for this disease were analyzed by Southern blot, long PCR (6, 18), and/or MLPA. We analyzed the presence of CNVs in all samples using the corresponding MLPA kit. Alterations in chr17 affecting the *TP53* gene were analyzed by FISH in 28 samples (8 with alterations in >70% of the cells and 20 without). Interphase FISH was performed on peripheral blood obtained at diagnosis using a 17p13/*TP53* probe (Vysis/Abbott Laboratories Co), following manufacturer's instructions.

PCR CONDITIONS

We performed a PCR mix including HotstarTaq DNA Polymerase (Qiagen) with minor modifications. Specific primer (Integrated DNA Technologies) concentrations were between 1 and 60 nM, and probe (Applied Biosystems) concentrations were between 3 and 7 times lower than specific primers.

We used the following PCR conditions: initial denaturing and activating step (95°C for 900 s), 10 cycles (98°C for 30 s, 62°C for 30 s, and 72°C for 50 s), 20 cycles (98°C for 30 s, 65°C for 30 s, and 72°C for 50 s), and a final extension step (72°C for 300 s).

DATA ANALYSIS

Data analysis included internal controls in each reaction and the 3 external controls in duplicate. This analysis was based on the following calculations (Fig. 2):

- Peak normalization (peak ratio): the area of each fragment of interest divided by the total area of control fragments and by the number of control fragments (Fig. 2, B)
- Mean of the peak ratio of each peak in control samples
- Peak ratio of each peak for each duplicate of problem samples
- Percentage of deviation from normal data, calculated as the ratio between the peak ratio of each peak for each

duplicate of problem samples (NPn) and the mean of the peak ratio of each peak in control samples (NCn) minus 1 and then multiplied by 100 from normal data: $[(NPn/NCn) - 1] \times 100$ (Fig. 2, C)

- Mean of the percentages of deviation from normal data for each fragment from each sample (Fig. 2, D)

These steps could be performed in a simple Microsoft Excel spreadsheet or with EOSAL-CNV analysis software (31).

Results

The EOSAL-CNV procedure allowed reliable CNV detection by a single PCR and fragment analysis in a capillary DNA sequencer.

NORMALIZATION AND REPRODUCIBILITY

Internal controls were included to normalize peak areas and reduce variability caused by handling or small differences between samples. For CNV detection, we needed to use values to identify normal peak distribution; therefore, we included external controls without CNVs in the target regions in each experiment. This approach allowed us to establish the percentage variation of each fragment to the normal values, the percentage of deviation, and the mean of the percentages of deviation (Fig. 2). These normalization steps allowed us to identify the degree of change from normal amplification.

Peak amplification variability within a PCR multiplex is a potential drawback and may interfere with CNV detection. One cause could be variation of peak ratios depending on the quantity of DNA used in a reaction. Therefore, we tested whether the procedure could detect CNVs using a wide range of DNA quantities (3.0 to 400 ng of DNA per reaction). We tested DNAs with and without CNVs (3 control DNAs, 1 sample with the insertion of exons 3 and 4 in 1 allele, and 1 sample with deletion of exons 3–10 in the *LDLR* gene) and 3 external controls. Our results showed that EOSAL-CNV allowed detection of CNVs in a wide range of DNA, at least between 12.5 and 400 ng (see Supplemental Fig. 1). Another problem could be the possible influence of small differences in DNA concentration between the samples used in 1 experiment: we analyzed previous data normalized by external controls with 25 ng per reaction. These results indicated that we could analyze samples and detect CNVs with different starting material, at least from 12.5 to 100 ng per reaction when external controls were used at 25 ng per reaction. These data showed that EOSAL-CNV afforded reliable results and facilitated the study of a wide range of DNA, even within the same experiment (see Supplemental Fig. 2).

Another primary source of variability in PCR multiplex may be the differences in laboratory

Fig. 2. Representation of peak areas, normalization, and deviation percentage of 5 samples analyzed in duplicate for the analysis of the *LDLR* gene. (A) Peak areas for each replicate of samples without normalization. (B) Peak ratios of replicates after internal normalization (NPN value). (C) Percentage of deviation from normal values of peak ratios obtained in each of the replicates for each sample after normalization with values for mean of the peak ratio of each peak in control samples. (D) Mean of the percentages of deviation from normal values for each peak obtained in each sample and standard deviation (indicated as vertical bars). The figures include control peaks and are ordered by size. C1, C2, and C3 are control samples used for normalization; S1 is a normal sample (without CNV in the *LDLR* gene), and S2 is a sample with duplication of exons 3 and 4. E indicates exon; L1, Laboratory 1; L2, Laboratory 2; M1, sample with deletion of exons 4–6; M2, results of sample with *LDLR* complete deletion; M3, wild-type sample for the *LDLR* gene; NPN indicates normalized peak values for each amplicon; P-C, mean of control samples.

environments, predominantly the use of thermocyclers with distinct heating and cooling ramps. Therefore, we performed 2 studies. First, we tested whether we could obtain similar results in 3 different experiments: we analyzed 3 samples, each one in duplicate, in 3 independent experiments (repeating the same experiment on 3 different days) using 3 different thermocyclers of the same

model and 2 different groups of fragments (one for the *LDLR* gene and another for *BRCA2-CHEK2*). Second, we tested whether different conditions in 2 different laboratories, including different thermocyclers (with major differences in temperature ramps, 96-well Applied Biosystems 2720 and Veriti), would modify the results. We tested the *LDLR* gene in 6 different samples: 4

healthy (3 for normalization) and 2 with different CNVs (complete deletion and deletion of exons 4–6 of the *LRLR* gene).

In the first study, we found variation of <5% among the results obtained in each experiment (Fig. 3, A and B). In the second study, we found similar results, although there were small differences in peak profiles between experiments (Fig. 3, C–F). Results analysis of each condition showed low variation between replicates, and relative and proportional amplification was maintained in both experiments. Consequently, both experiments allowed CNV analysis.

Once the conditions for CNV detection (heterozygous alterations) were established, we assessed the reliability of the technique. We analyzed different control samples without CNVs in the *LDLR* gene and DNA from patients with different CNVs in this gene. We analyzed 25 wild-type samples and 23 samples with 7 different CNVs in the *LDLR* gene (Fig. 4). Our results showed that the mean of the percentages of deviation of peaks without CNVs were located between –20% and +20%. Heterozygous deletion was in the region between –35% and –65%, whereas heterozygous insertions were between +35% and +65%. Our results indicated that there was a wide region without peaks, eliminating misclassification of any peak (areas between 20% and 35% and –20% and –35%) (Fig. 4). Therefore, we selected a cutoff of $\pm 35\%$ for *LDLR* for heterozygous CNV detection. Last, Fig. 4D shows that results from experiments performed in similar conditions could be analyzed together after normalization.

To simplify data analysis, we developed a simple tool for representing the results that provided identification and description of alterations (EOSAL-CNV analysis software, Sequencing Multiplex SL), as shown in Fig. 5 and online Supplemental Fig. 3.

COMPARISON WITH MLPA AND FISH

Finally, to demonstrate our system's ability to detect CNVs in other genes, we analyzed the genes indicated in the following multiplexes: *BRCA1*, *BRCA2-CHEK2*, *EPCAM-MSH2*, *MLH1-MSH6*, and chr17 (focused on the 17p region and *TP53*). We optimized reactions to amplify all desired fragments with 25 ng of genomic DNA and confirmed that the expected changes in peak area occurred using 12.5 and 50 ng of DNA.

All samples for each of the genes indicated (including samples for the *LDLR* gene) were analyzed with EOSAL-CNV (Fig. 5 and Supplemental Fig. 3) and MLPA or FISH (see Supplemental Table 2). No CNV was detected in control samples. In samples with CNVs, all results performed in our laboratory were concordant between EOSAL-CNV and MLPA. From these samples, 2 could not be analyzed by either method and 3 gave normal results (without any CNV): 2 in *BRCA1*

Fig. 3. Intra- and interlaboratory reproducibility of PCR multiplex amplification and labeling. (A) Graphical representation of the peak areas obtained in the *LDLR* gene using 3 different thermocyclers (T1, T2, and T3; same model) at different time points. (B) Graphical representation of the peak areas obtained in the *BRCA2-CHEK2* gene analysis in the same conditions as (A). (C) Normalized peak profile of control samples used in Laboratory 1 analysis (C1, C2, and C3; Veriti thermocycler, Thermo Fisher). (D) Normalized peak profile of control samples used in Laboratory 2 analysis (Applied Biosystems 2720 thermocycler, Thermo Fisher). (E) Profile of normalized peaks from the 3 controls (mean) and from 3 different samples, 2 with rearrangements obtained in Laboratory 1. (F) Profile of normalized peaks of the same samples obtained in Laboratory 2. The bars represent the mean of 2 replicas, and vertical lines represent the standard deviation. C1, C2, and C3 are control samples used for normalization; S1 is a normal sample (without CNV in the *LDLR* gene), and S2 is a sample with duplication of exons 3 and 4. PD, percentage of deviation; PM, mean of percentages of deviation.

Fig. 4. Reliability of EOSAL-CNV for analysis of normal and CNV carriers in the *LDLR* gene. (A) Representation of percentage of deviation of normal (PDn) corresponding to *LDLR* gene peaks in samples without CNVs. (B) Experiment with 6 healthy samples without CNVs and 11 samples with 5 different CNVs. (C) Experiment with 5 wild-type samples and 3 samples with 2 different CNVs. (D) PDn representation corresponding to 4 different experiments including 20 wild-type samples and 20 samples with 7 different CNVs; heterozygous duplication, normal, and heterozygous deletion areas are delimited by upper, middle, and lower rectangles, respectively. Each color point represents a sample, and each dot represents the mean value of duplicates for each sample. E, exon; PM, mean of percentages of deviation.

and 1 in *BRCA2*. All remaining samples agreed between previous data and results with EOSAL-CNV and MLPA (see Supplemental Table 2).

Samples included in the study of chr17 were analyzed by FISH, which is the gold standard for these analyses in chronic lymphocytic leukemia, so we compared our results with this technique. We selected samples with CNV present in >70% of cells to apply the same criteria for CNV detection used for the remaining genes. Our results were compatible with those found by FISH in all cases.

Discussion

CNVs are a major form of genetic variation in mammals and are causative of many human diseases, making CNV assessment an important part of genetic diagnosis and research in a myriad of genetic diseases (32, 33). We have developed an easy, fast, and reliable procedure for CNV detection using a single PCR and fragment analysis system. The procedure is based on proportional amplification and labeling of each amplicon in a single

multiplex PCR reaction by only 1 labeled probe (Fig. 1). The protocol requires only adding the DNA sample to a reaction mix, performing PCR cycles, loading onto a capillary DNA sequencer, and analyzing the data (Fig. 6). The results can be obtained in 2.5 h with <10 min of handwork. In addition, data analysis can be done using a simple calculation system in Microsoft Excel or our EOSAL-CNV analysis software (28), which simplifies the procedure.

The main techniques comparable to EOSAL-CNV are QMPSF, MAQ, UPQFM-PCR, and MLPA. QMPSF and MAQ are based on a PCR multiplex with a fluorescent-labeled primer for each amplicon and fragment analysis by a DNA sequencer. UPQFM-PCR is based on 2 consecutive PCR reactions, the first with specific primers with a universal tail and the second with universal primers, one of which is fluorescent-labeled, and final analysis of PCR products in a DNA sequencer (17). UPQFM-PCR was improved by including internal and external controls (18). QMPSF and MAQ procedures are expensive because they require a large number of labeled primers, and UPQFM-PCR

Fig. 5. Examples of CNV detection in the genes tested. Comparison of wild-type and altered sample fluorograms (moved slightly to the right and marked in red) and visualization by EOSAL-CNV analysis software. (A) *BRCA1* gene analysis and example of CNV detection (exon 1–12 deletion). (B) *BRCA2* and *CHEK2* gene analysis and detection of exon 21–24 deletion in the *BRCA2* gene. (C) Analysis of *MLH1* and *MSH6* genes and detection of exon 1–7 deletion in the *MSH6* gene. (D) Analysis of *EPCAM* and *MSH2* genes for CNV detection (deletion from exons 8 of *EPCAM* to exon 2 of *MSH2*). (E) Analysis of region 17p and detection of with a deletion from *KIFC* to *MAP2K3* indicating the elimination of the whole 17p arm. Peaks with altered proportion and control peaks were identified by empty and filled circles, respectively. Bars indicate mean, and vertical line represents standard deviation. E, exon; *KIF1C*: kinesin family member 1C; *MAP2K3*: mitogen-activated protein kinase kinase 3 PM, mean of percentages of deviation.

Fig. 6. Schematic representation of EOSAL-CNV including the times required.

increases the amount of PCR reactions, turnaround time, and manual processing. These procedures are not routinely used because of limitations in design procedure and reproducibility (2). MLPA is based on DNA ligation and semiquantitative PCR amplification of the ligated probes (21). This system has greatly simplified CNV detection and has become the most widely used for genetic diagnosis in hereditary diseases, although it still requires several steps and reagents for hybridization, ligation, and PCR and is a lengthy process (up to 30 h). Protocols such as “3-primer protocols,” used for typing of short tandem repeats, have not been used for CNV detection (34), probably because of variation in amplification of each fragment due to the use of different primers in one end of each amplicon. Using this terminology, EOSAL-CNV could be classed as a “4-primer protocol.”

We used the procedure to analyze up to 30 amplicons in 1 reaction (the number required for *BRCA2* analysis). The peaks in all reactions were detectable over 90 bp using a difference of 3 bp between each amplicon and allowed inclusion of larger number of fragments. Peak areas were variable, although the relation between peak intensities and profiles was reproducible in the same sample and between samples without CNVs or within samples with the same CNV in different experiments (Figs. 2 and 3). The use of internal and external controls allowed the normalization of each fragment by simple calculations and combination of experiments (Fig. 2, D).

EOSAL-CNV allows detection of CNVs working with 12.5 ng up to 400 ng of genomic DNA per reaction and with a wide range of DNA quantities in 1 experiment (see Supplemental Figs. 1 and 2). EOSAL works with samples obtained from fresh or frozen

samples; application to fragmented samples (from formalin-fixed paraffin-embedded samples) could be more limited than MLPA because of amplicon length. Use of PCR instead of ligation can facilitate the analysis of samples with different purity grades. Both techniques can be used to study regions rich in GC, but both require increased denaturalization before reactions. We used a higher denaturalization temperature than normal, although this may not be sufficient for specific regions. EOSAL-CNV can be used for allele-specific amplification (data not shown) such as MLPA. Therefore, both allow the study of genes having pseudogenes with minimal differences in sequence (1 or 2 bp per region of interest).

Similar to MLPA, QMPSF, MAQ, and UPQFM-PCR, EOSAL-CNV requires analysis of labeled amplicons in a DNA sequencer but avoids the need for other types of reactions (e.g., hybridization and ligation), a labeled primer for each amplicon to be analyzed, and the use of 2 consecutive PCRs. Our procedure achieves a 4- to 7-fold reduction in steps, reagents, laboratory consumables, and working time compared with MLPA, with similar cost savings. In addition, in our optimization procedure, a simple verification of peak intensity variation using different DNA quantities, allows the use of multiplexes for CNV detection.

In summary, our results show that EOSAL-CNV represents an excellent alternative for CNV detection and characterization or validation in genetic studies and can be incorporated into routine CNV screening in genetic studies for detection and results verification.

Supplemental Material

Supplemental material is available at *Clinical Chemistry* online.

Nonstandard abbreviations: CNV, copy number variation; OMIM, Online Mendelian Inheritance in Man; FH, familial hypercholesterolemia; FISH, fluorescence in situ hybridization; MLPA, multiplex ligation-dependent probe amplification; QMPSF, quantitative multiplex PCR of short fluorescent fragments; UPQFM-PCR, universal primer quantitative fluorescent multiplex PCR; MAQ, multiplex amplicon quantification; EOSAL-CNV, Easy One-Step Amplification and Labeling procedure for CNV detection.

Human genes: *LDLR*, low density lipoprotein receptor; *BRCA1*, BRCA1 DNA repair associated; *BRCA2*, BRCA2 DNA repair associated; *CHEK2*, checkpoint kinase 2; *MLH1*, mutL homolog 1; *MSH2*, mutS homolog 2; *EPCAM*, epithelial cell adhesion molecule; *MSH6*, mutS homolog 6; *TP53*, tumor protein p53; *KIF1C*, kinesin family member 1C; *MAP2K3*, mitogen-activated protein kinase 3.

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References

- Alkan C, Coe BP, Eichler EE. Genome structural variation discovery and genotyping. *Nat Rev Genet* 2011;12:363-76.
- Ceulemans S, van der Ven K, Del-Favero J. Targeted screening and validation of copy number variations. *Methods Mol Biol* 2012;838:311-28.
- Iafate AJ, Feuk L, Rivera MN, Listewnik ML, Donahoe PK, Qi Y, et al. Detection of large-scale variation in the human genome. *Nat Genet* 2004;36:949-51.
- Sebat J, Lakshmi B, Troge J, Alexander J, Young J, Lundin P, et al. Large-scale copy number polymorphism in the human genome. *Science* 2004;305:525-8.
- Redón R, Ishikawa S, Fitch KR, Feuk L, Perry GH, Andrews TD, et al. Global variation in copy number in the human genome. *Nature* 2006;444:444-54.
- Chaves FJ, Real JT, García-García AB, Puig O, Ordoñez JM, Ascaso JF, et al. Large rearrangements of the LDL receptor gene and lipid profile in a FH Spanish population. *Eur J Clin Invest* 2001;31:309-17.
- Payne SR, Newman B, King MC. Complex germline rearrangement of BRCA1 associated with breast and ovarian cancer. *Genes Chromosomes Cancer* 2000;29:58-62.
- van der Klift H, Wijnen J, Wagner A, Verkuilen P, Tops C, Otway R, et al. Molecular characterization of the spectrum of genomic deletions in the mismatch repair genes

- MSH2, MLH1, MSH6, and PMS2 responsible for hereditary nonpolyposis colorectal cancer (HNPCC). *Genes Chromosomes Cancer* 2005;44:123-38.
9. Wei R, Zhao M, Zheng CH, Zhao M, Xia J. Concordance between somatic copy number loss and down-regulated expression: a pan-cancer study of cancer predisposition genes. *Sci Rep* 2016;6:37358.
 10. Riegel M. Human molecular cytogenetics: from cells to nucleotides. *Genet Mol Biol* 2014;37:194-209.
 11. Silva M, de Leeuw N, Mann K, Schuring-Blom H, Morgan S, Giardino D, et al. European guidelines for constitutional cytogenomic analysis. *Eur J Hum Genet* 2019;27:1-16.
 12. Jahnke K, Burmeister T, Korfel A, Coupland SE, Thiel E. Long distance polymerase chain reaction of ascites lymphoma cells aids diagnosis establishment of abdominal Burkitt's lymphoma and Burkitt-like lymphoma. *Leuk Lymphoma* 2005;46:83-6.
 13. Casilli F, Di Rocco ZC, Gad S, Tournier I, Stoppa-Lyonnet D, Frebourg T, Tosi M. Rapid detection of novel BRCA1 rearrangements in high-risk breast-ovarian cancer families using multiplex PCR of short fluorescent fragments. *Hum Mutat* 2002;20:218-26.
 14. Barrois M, Bièche I, Mazoyer S, Champème MH, Bressac-de Paillerets B, Lidereau R. Real-time PCR-based gene dosage assay for detecting BRCA1 rearrangements in breast-ovarian cancer families. *Clin Genet* 2004;65:131-6.
 15. Cantafora A, Blotta I, Pino E, Pisciotta L, Calandra S, Bertolini S. Quantitative polymerase chain reaction and microchip electrophoresis to detect major rearrangements of the low-density lipoprotein receptor gene causing familial hypercholesterolemia. *Electrophoresis* 2004;25:3882-9.
 16. Ariani F, Mari F, Pescucci C, Longo I, Bruttini M, Meloni I, et al. Real-time quantitative PCR as a routine method for screening large rearrangements in Rett syndrome: report of one case of MECP2 deletion and one case of MECP2 duplication. *Hum Mutat* 2004;24:172-7.
 17. Heath KE, Day IN, Humphries SE. Universal primer quantitative fluorescent multiplex (UPOFM) PCR: a method to detect major and minor rearrangements of the low density lipoprotein receptor gene. *J Med Genet* 2000;37:272-80.
 18. Garcia-Garcia AB, Blesa S, Martinez-Hervas S, Mansego ML, Gonzalez-Albert V, Ascaso JF, et al. Semiquantitative multiplex PCR: a useful tool for large rearrangement screening and characterization. *Hum Mutat* 2006;27:822-8.
 19. Saxena S, Gowdhaman K, Kkani P, Vennapusa B, Rama Subramanian C, Ganesh Kumar S, Mohan KN. Improved multiplex ligation-dependent probe amplification (i-MLPA) for rapid copy number variant (CNV) detection. *Clin Chim Acta* 2015;450:19-24.
 20. Gille JJ, Hogervorst FB, Pals G, Wijnen JT, van Schooten RJ, Dommering CJ, et al. Genomic deletions of MSH2 and MLH1 in colorectal cancer families detected by a novel mutation detection approach. *Br J Cancer* 2002;87:892-7.
 21. Schouten JP, McElgunn CJ, Waaijer R, Zwijnenburg D, Diepvens F, Pals G. Relative quantification of 40 nucleic acid sequences by multiplex ligation-dependent probe amplification. *Nucleic Acids Res* 2002;30:e57.
 22. Frolov A, Prowse AH, Vanderveer L, Bove B, Wu H, Godwin AK. DNA array-based method for detection of large rearrangements in the BRCA1 gene. *Genes Chromosomes Cancer* 2002;35:232-41.
 23. Yang S, Wang K, Gregory B, Berrettini W, Wang LS, Hakonarson H, Bucan M. Genomic landscape of a three-generation pedigree segregating affective disorder. *PLoS One* 2009;4:e4474.
 24. Mardis ER, Ding L, Dooling DJ, Larson DE, McLellan MD, Chen K, et al. Recurring mutations found by sequencing an acute myeloid leukemia genome. *N Engl J Med* 2009;361:1058-66.
 25. Rouleau E, Jesson B, Briaux A, Nogues C, Chabaud V, Demange L, et al. Rare germline large rearrangements in the BRCA1/2 genes and eight candidate genes in 472 patients with breast cancer predisposition. *Breast Cancer Res Treat* 2012;133:1179-90.
 26. Li S, Dou X, Gao R, Ge X, Qian M, Wan L. A remark on copy number variation detection methods. *PLoS One* 2018;13:e0196226.
 27. Haraksingh RR, Abyzov A, Urban AE. Comprehensive performance comparison of high-resolution array platforms for genome-wide copy number variation (CNV) analysis in humans. *BMC Genomics* 2017;18:321-35.
 28. Xu L, Hou Y, Bickhart DM, Song J, Liu GE. Comparative analysis of CNV calling algorithms: literature survey and a case study using bovine high-density SNP data. *Microarrays (Basel)* 2013;2:171-85.
 29. Yao R, Zhang C, Yu T, Li N, Hu X, Wang X, et al. Evaluation of three read-depth based CNV detection tools using whole-exome sequencing data. *Mol Cytogenet* 2017;10:30.
 30. Untergasser A, Cutcutache I, Koressaar T, Ye J, Faircloth BC, Remm M, Rozen SG. Primer3-new capabilities and interfaces. *Nucleic Acids Res* 2012;40:e115.
 31. Sequencing Multiplex SL User Zone. <https://www.sequencing.com/en/users> (Accessed August 2016).
 32. Zhang F, Gu W, Hurles ME, Lupski JR. Copy number variation in human health, disease and evolution. *Annu Rev Genom Hum Genet* 2009;10:451-81.
 33. Stankiewicz P, Lupski JR. Structural variation in the human genome and its role in disease. *Annu Rev Med* 2010;61:437-55.
 34. Blacket MJ, Robin C, Good RT, Lee SF, Miller AD. Universal primers for fluorescent labelling of PCR fragments-an efficient and cost-effective approach to genotyping by fluorescence. *Mol Ecol Resour* 2012;12:456-63.